

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN LITERARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of information technologies in the education system, their impact on the quality and efficiency of education, the achievements of the formation of competencies in information technologies among students, and the types of lessons in which information technologies are introduced.

Keywords: digital technology, websites, online lessons

The development of new-age education is associated with the use of informatics and information technologies in the education system. "In the 21st century, in technically developed countries, the main part of information is stored in paperless form - in the memory of computers. Therefore, a person who cannot use this information at the beginning of the 21st century will be like a person who cannot read or write at the beginning of the 20th century," says Glushkov. Today's information technology tools include: the Internet and Internet networks, e-mail, fax modem, video camera, information systems, telephone, electronic board, laptop, mobile applications, satellite communication systems, data warehouse management systems, innovative technologies for artificial intelligence systems and methods, various teaching methods (traditional and non-traditional), local and global networks, distance learning, telecommunications, video conferencing, chat, forums.

The main features of the Internet are:

- the ability to transfer information at high speed;
- the ability to work with multimedia and hypertext;
- the two-way nature of telecommunications, which provides interactivity;
- the provision of a user-friendly interface when working with complex structured information.

It is very gratifying that similar conveniences are being introduced in the school education system. In particular, the new textbook provides convenience for students by providing QR codes and scanners in a position appropriate to the topic. We can find such places in the literature textbook published for the 10th grade of general secondary schools. According to it, under the excerpt from the epic poem "Saddi Iskandariy" by Alisher Navoi, the following task is given:

"Watch the play "Iskandar" staged at the Uzbek State Drama Theater named after Abror Hidoyatov based on the epic poem "Saddi Iskandariy". Pay

attention to the interpretation of the images of Alisher Navoi and Iskandar in the play. In what ways does Iskandar in the play differ from Iskandar in the epic poem? Why do you think the image of Navoi was introduced into the work?"¹

“Saddi Iskandariy” dostoni asosida Abror Hidoyatov nomidagi o‘zbek davlat drama teatrida sahnalashtirilgan “Iskandar” spektaklini tomosha qiling. Spektakldagi Alisher Navoiy va Iskandar obrazlari talqiniga e’tibor bering. Spektakldagi Iskandar dostonidagi Iskandardan qaysi jihatlari bilan farq qiladi? Asarga Navoiy obrazi nima uchun olib kirilgan deb o‘ylaysiz?

Alisher Navoiy “Xamsa”sining Anvar Hojiahmedov tomonidan tayyorlangan nasriy bayonini o‘qib chiqishingizni tavsiya qilamiz.

By scanning these QR codes, students can easily find the above materials.

In our republic, improving the quality of the Internet in the integration of information technologies into the education system and training programmers related to the field of education are among the most urgent issues. That is why a number of reforms are being implemented in this direction in our country. In his address to the Oliy Majlis, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized the need to introduce information technologies in the implementation of the “One Million Programmers” project together with foreign partners in order to digitize the education system, as well as all sectors, and to train highly qualified specialists for the education system.

The next main feature in the introduction of information technologies into the education system is the personality of the teacher and the student. In order to implement a modern education system, it is necessary to develop competencies in mastering these technologies, first of all, in the teacher, and then in the student receiving the knowledge. There are opportunities to implement literature lessons in school education in an effective and interesting way using information technologies. Their Some of the types are:

1. Using educational websites.
2. Organizing online classes.
3. Organizing virtual tours of museums.
4. Using mobile applications related to literature.

Using digital technologies in the education system means organizing a modern education system based on digital technologies.

If in past centuries, people who knew how to read and write were considered literate, today's generation is required to acquire and constantly develop media literacy, or rather, the competence to apply information and communication technologies in practice. “ The time is coming and even passing to develop the skills of understanding, understanding and adapting to the digital age”². Today, in the Internet age, in order to educate the growing generation, a teacher must have mastered media literacy at a high level.

One of the most urgent issues in integrating information technologies into the education system in our republic is improving the quality of Internet services and training programmers. Multimedia is a type of information technology that allows the application of all subjects of literary science. Multimedia can be used to vividly present topics, in particular, lessons dedicated to Navoi's works, and organize the lesson in an interesting way.

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